

INTER- AND INTRA-LAMINAR DYNAMIC FRACTURE OF CFRP WITH AND WITHOUT CNT MODIFICATION OF EPOXY: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In this work, mode-I dynamic interlaminar and intralaminar fracture behaviors of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are studied. Thick unidirectional composites were processed and their fracture performance was characterized under both quasi-static three-point bending and dynamic one-point impact loading conditions. Both crack initiation and growth characteristics under stress-wave dominant loading conditions were evaluated in the latter case. The optical methods of digital image correlation (DIC) and ultra-high speed photography were employed to monitor crack tip deformations around transiently growing cracks. Interlaminar fracture responses were compared to the intralaminar counterparts using specimens of identical dimensions from the same original composite sheet. To author's knowledge, this will be the first work to compare interlaminar and intralaminar fracture of unidirectional samples cut from the same composite sheet and using the same test geometry.

1 INTRODUCTION

Several authors¹⁻⁴ have compared intralaminar and interlaminar crack growth of unidirectional composites; however, to author's knowledge, none have used the same geometry when comparing intralaminar and interlaminar specimens. Most^{1,2,4} used double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens to examine interlaminar fracture and compact tension specimens to examine intralaminar fracture, whereas De Moura³ used DCB specimens of different geometries to examine interlaminar and intralaminar fracture. Because measured stress intensity factors (SIFs) are dependent on geometry, the present work involves the fabrication of thick carbon fiber composites such that both interlaminar and intralaminar specimens with the same geometry can be prepared from the same sheet and tested under similar conditions.

This will also be the first work to use DIC to map full-field deformations before and after crack initiation in order to determine interlaminar SIF histories in composite specimens. A few previous works on this topic⁵⁻⁸ have employed strain gages to evaluate dynamic fracture parameters. The advantage of the optical methods used in this work is that, unlike strain gages, they provide non-contact full-field deformations as well as the precise location of the crack tip during the fracture event, which is necessary for estimating crack tip velocities for an accurate evaluation of dynamic SIF histories and hence crack growth resistance.

2 SPECIMEN PREPARATIONS

Sixty unidirectional carbon fiber sheets (V-Web 900 from V2 Composites, 200 mm x 200 mm) were stacked, with stoichiometric mixture of Epon 862 resin and Epikure W curing agent painted between each layer (Fig. 1a). The resulting CFRP was ~17 mm thick. Dynamic fracture samples (50 mm x 50 mm x 6 mm) for interlaminar and intralaminar fracture evaluation were then machined from the cured sheet into blocks as shown in Fig. 1. Three interlaminar slices were stacked vertically and

adhered using the same epoxy system in order to achieve these dimensions for performing dynamic interlaminar fracture tests (Fig. 2). Similarly, quasi-static 3-point bend specimens (60 mm x 15 mm x 5 mm) were machined in order to examine both interlaminar and intralaminar fracture. Again, pre-notches were oriented parallel to the fiber direction. In all cases, the initial CFRP was cured for 2.5 hours at 120°C, whereas the final fracture specimens were post-cured for 3 hours at 180°C.

Figure 1: (a) Wet layup procedure for 60-layer CFRPs. (b) Orientation of interlaminar and intralaminar slices from the same thick composite sheet.

Figure 2: (a) Dimensions of a single dynamic interlaminar slice machined from the CFRP manufactured in Fig. 1b. (b) Preparation of dynamic interlaminar fracture specimens by stacking and gluing three blocks with the dimensions shown in (a).

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Quasi-static 3-point bend configuration is given in Figure 3a. Dynamic 1-point impact tests were performed using a Hopkinson pressure bar (long-bar), depicted in Figure 3b. Compressed air is used to launch a striker (25.4 mm diameter, 0.30 m length) coaxially towards the long-bar (25.4 mm diameter, 1.83 m length) of the same material (strain-rate independent aluminum 7075 T6). A soft aluminum pulse shaper was used between the striker and the long-bar to temper the loading rate such that more images could be captured in the pre- and post-initiation phases of the dynamic fracture event. The long-bar has a semi-circular (cylindrical) head machined on the end initially in contact with the specimen in order to deliver thickness-wise line-loading (1-point impact) to the specimen. The compressive stress wave travels across the specimen, reaches the free edge with the pre-notch, reflects back as a tensile wave, opens the pre-notch, initiates crack growth, and drives the crack to velocities as high as 800 m/s, all while inertia is holding the specimen within the view of the ultra-high speed camera. A roller of putty is placed above and below the specimen for the purpose of specimen alignment and in order to ensure symmetric wave reflections from the top and bottom surfaces of the specimen under “free-free” conditions. A Cordin ultrahigh speed camera collects 32 digital images

during the fracture event at 300,000 frames per second. A strain gage on the long-bar is used to collect stress wave data for independent estimation of SIFs prior to crack initiation using finite element analysis (FEA) software (see Section 3.5).

Figure 3: Specimen and experimental setup details: (a) Quasi-static 3-point bending of edge-cracked specimen and (b) Dynamic 1-point impact of edge-cracked specimen.

4 RESULTS

Figure 3a contains three sample digital images of the speckle decoration on the specimen recorded 0, 6.6, and 13.1 μ s after crack initiation during a dynamic interlaminar fracture test. The arrow indicates the current location of the crack tip. Figures 3b and 3c show the corresponding crack opening (Fig. 3b) and crack sliding (Fig. 3c) displacements determined from 2D DIC. Using these displacements and an over-deterministic least squares analysis based on dynamic crack tip fields in orthotropic materials, mode-I SIFs (K_I) were obtained for each recorded image. Crack initiation SIFs were obtained from the image before crack initiation (K_{IC} for quasi-static tests and K_{I-ini}^d for dynamic tests).

Orthotropic material properties were determined ultrasonically⁹ (Table 1). These properties were then used, along with the displacement fields from DIC (Fig. 3) and an overdeterministic least squares analysis, to determine mode-I SIFs for each image captured during the fracture event. Figure 5 gives the SIF histories for growing cracks in three specimens subjected to quasi-static mode-I loading (framing rate = 1 frame every 3 seconds). The open symbols denote crack initiation for each of three tests. The average crack initiation SIF is significantly higher for intralaminar (Fig. 5a) specimens than interlaminar specimen geometries (Fig. 5b).

Figure 4: Full-field measurement of deformations using DIC: (a) Three of 32 images collected during an interlaminar dynamic fracture test of neat epoxy/carbon fiber, (b) ν -opening contours of displacement, and (c) u -sliding contours of displacement. The crack initiates at time $t=0$. Contour interval is $10 \mu\text{m}$.

Test Type	Crack Propagation Modulus	Crack Opening Modulus	Shear Modulus	Poisson's Ratio
Intralaminar	$E_1 = 94.54$ [GPa]	$E_2 = 8.29$ [GPa]	$G_{12} = 5.31$ [GPa]	$\nu_{12} = 0.42$
Interlaminar	$E_1 = 94.54$ [GPa]	$E_3 = 7.10$ [GPa]	$G_{13} = 4.32$ [GPa]	$\nu_{13} = 0.52$

Table 1: Ultrasonically determined orthotropic elastic constants.

Figure 5: Stress intensity factor histories (SIFs) for the quasi-static fracture of intralaminar (Fig. 5a) and interlaminar specimens (Fig. 5b). Open symbols denote crack initiation.

Figure 6 shows the SIF histories for growing cracks subjected to dynamic mode-I loading, recorded at 300,000 frames per second. The open symbols denote crack initiation for each of three tests. The average crack initiation SIF is significantly higher for intralaminar (Fig. 6a) specimens than interlaminar counterparts (Fig. 6b). Further, intralaminar SIF histories show a relatively higher crack growth resistance in the post-initiation regime when compared to the interlaminar cases. These effects are likely due to the lightweight fiberglass scrim that is used to hold the unidirectional fabric together; intralaminar cracks must propagate through these stitches, whereas interlaminar cracks propagate between the layers of carbon fiber.

Figure 6: Stress intensity factor histories (SIFs) for the dynamic fracture of intralaminar (Fig. 6a) and interlaminar specimens (Fig. 6b). Open symbols denote crack initiation.

4 ONGOING RESEARCH

With the goal of improving the interlaminar fracture performance, micro- and nano-fillers are dispersed into the epoxy resin. Then three-phase carbon fiber composites have been processed using the same wet layup procedure as before. The micro-fillers are milled carbon fibers ($\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ in length and $8 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter), whereas the nanoparticles are NH_2 -functionalized CNTs ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$ in length and 9 nm in diameter). Currently, analysis is underway to study the efficacy of micro- and nano-bridges on

interlaminar fracture mitigation. This will be the first attempt to examine the ability of micro- and nano-fillers to enhance the interlaminar fracture properties of CFRPs under impact loading conditions.

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